

Gingival Mask- A Case Report on Recreating Smiles

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ABSTRACT

Esthetics is most important consent by the people. To maintain a proper oral cavity, we need take care of the and gums. The periodontal attachment loss, gingival recession and loss of interdental papilla in the maxillary anterior region can often lead to aesthetic and functional problems. It becomes a challenge for the dentist to provide an aesthetic solution for maintain hygiene and the recreation of the missing gingival tissue. Gingival prostheses may be fixed or removable and may be made from acrylics, composite resins, silicones or porcelain-based materials. Undercuts or dental attachments are used to secure removable prostheses, which are esthetically pleasing and easy to maintain. In This case report describes the fabrication of an esthetic and soft flexible thermoplastic gingival veneer in a chronic periodontitis patient providing an economical and esthetically acceptable solution for spacing between the anteriors.

Keywords: Gingival masks, Esthetics, Gingival Recession, Removable prosthesis, Black triangle.

INTRODUCTION

Gingival recession is one of the most common clinical manifestation of all the oral diseases. Gingival replacement prostheses have historically been used to replace lost tissue when other methods (e.g., surgery) are considered unpredictable or impossible for so many reasons. With this method, large tissue volumes are easily preserved without any major surgical procedures in the anterior region.

Gingival prostheses were made in several forms, and various authors have described their uses and different methods of construction. ^[1] A gratifying smile is an assembly of various components. Marginal gingiva and interdental papilla, having high esthetic value. Gingival recession can cause loss of inter-dental papilla and that will lead to open embrasures, which project in the form of black triangles, especially in the anteriors. The black triangles that appear as a result of gingival recession will distort an unpleasant smile.

CASE REPORT

A 34-year-old female presented with esthetic and phonetic problems. The patient had recently undergone periodontal surgery with respect to 11 and 21, which eventually resulted in the loss of interdental papillae between maxillary central incisors after 2 months (Figure 1). The first option is mucogingival surgery or gingival plastic surgery, with gingival augmentation coronal to the recession. This is suitable for class I and class II type of gingival recessions. ^[2]

In severe gingival recession conditions, as in class III and class IV recessions (Millers classification of gingival recession) as seen in this patient, mucogingival surgeries may give less predictable esthetic results or might cause a recurrence. The second option, gingival replacement with artificial substitutes, is more helpful in managing severe gingival recession situations. The synonyms of gingival mask are flange prosthesis, gingival veneer, gingival veneer prosthesis, gingival replacement unit, and artificial gingiva.

This case report describes the use of a gingival veneer to hide the deformities in a young female patient with pleasing smile. The gingival replacement unit should be fabricated 2-3 months following initial periodontal treatment to allow the gingiva to stabilize. But in certain situations, the mask can be used as an interim measure to improve the esthetics of anterior crowns after initial periodontal therapy to allow time for healing and the establishment of periodontal stability and prognosis. In this way, the patient's smile can be maintained while the final treatment planning decisions are delayed until the periodontal prognosis is established.

Indications for the removable gingival mask:

1. To cover-exposed crown margins, exposed implant components and root surfaces and reduce the length of the clinical crown.
2. To block out the black triangles between teeth in which gingival recession has occurred.
3. To fill in the space between the crown and the soft tissue.
4. To prevent airflow through or beneath maxillary fixed restorations or through the spaces between the teeth and thus improving phonetics.
5. To provide increased lip and cheek support for those patients who require it.
6. It is also beneficial for patients with high lip lines and a gummy smile who have been treated with osseointegrated dental implants.
7. To hide the dark lines around old crowns that are often seen with patients who have experienced gingival recession.
8. It also aids the prosthodontist to design implant supported prosthesis with optimal configurations permitting easy access for oral hygiene maintenance.

The gingival mask is contra-indicated in patients with poor plaque control, unstable periodontal health, high caries activity, smoking, and known allergy to acrylic or silicone.

The gingival mask is retained mechanically with tiny extensions of the mask material slightly projecting between the roots of the natural teeth or the implants just above the gum line. Part of the retention also comes from the

natural capillary action created by the saliva and lastly part of the retention is dependent on the pressure of the lips against the gingival prosthesis.

A treatment plan was established involving the following steps:

1. The topography of the soft tissue defect was evaluated.
2. The color of the soft tissue was determined to achieve the acceptable esthetics.
3. Photographs were taken to replicate the similar color in the gingival mask.

For gingival veneer, master impression with a complete inter proximal detail was made. The lingual embrasures were blocked using utility wax. A custom tray was used to make a final impression using polyether impression material. After the casts were made, it was followed by construction of wax-up try-in on this model (Figure 2).

This wax-up was then duplicated to form removable prosthesis with (Figures 3,4). The prosthesis was extended up to the mesial aspects of first premolars bilaterally. This seemed to be necessary considering the patient's smile window. The distal most portions of the prosthesis were thinned out in order to be blended with given to clean it every time after having food and to remove the prosthesis at night. This would also ensure adequate rest to the gingival tissues. The importance of persistent plaque control in the ongoing prevention of both caries and periodontal disease was emphasized.

Figure 1: Pre operative view

Figure 2: Wax-up of the gingival mask

Figure 3: Fabricated gingival mask

Figure 4: Post operative view

DISCUSSION

Gingival defects may be treated with surgical or prosthetic approaches. With successful surgical treatment, the result mimics the original tissue contours. But the surgical costs, healing time, discomfort and unpredictability make this choice unpopular.

Prosthetic replacement, with acrylics, composite resins, porcelains and silicones, is a more predictable approach to replacing lost tissue architecture. It is especially useful when a larger amount of tissue needs replacement. Ideal tissue contours can be waxed, processed and then colored to match the surrounding tissue. The patient need not undergo any additional surgical procedures and receives an esthetically pleasing, functional restoration. It is possible to show the patient a waxed-up result or even take a try-in prosthesis directly to the mouth for evaluation before significant treatment is initiated.

Several materials are available for the fabrication of gingival veneer among all these materials, Hence, in the present case, the material was chosen to construct gingival veneer. Loss of interdental papillae in maxillary anterior region can often lead to esthetic and functional clinical problems. In such cases, it becomes a challenge for the dentist to provide optimum esthetic solution for the missing gingival tissues and at the same time preserve periodontal health. Gingival veneers are easy to fabricate and offer predictable and satisfactory results in the management of lost interdental papillae.

REFERENCES

1. Shah A. A case report gingival veneer: Non-invasive approach in the management of lost interdental papilla. Int J Dent Case Rep 2012;2: 54-58.
2. Ravi Shankar Y KS, Sumeet Kumar Sarma, Shameen Kumar P. Management of Black Triangles and Gingival Recession: A Prosthetic Approach. Indian Journal of Dental Sciences. 2012; 4(1).
3. Lakshman R, Rajashekar S, Vikas P. Gingival Cascade. An Esthetic solution in Dental Practise-A Case Report -JIDA 2011; 5:938-940.
4. Suvarna P, Vivek P, Nilima GV, Mask D. The unaesthetic. JOP 2011;15:284-287.
5. Studer S, Naef R, Schärer P. Adjustment of localized alveolar ridge defects by soft tissue transplantation to improve mucogingival esthetics: A proposal for clinical classification and an evaluation of procedures. Quintessence Int 1997;28:785-805.
6. Tallents RH. Artificial gingival replacements. Oral Health 1983;73:37-40.
7. Botha PJ, Gluckman HL. The gingival prosthesis: A literature review. SADJ 1999;54:288-290.
8. Friedman MJ. Gingival masks: A simple prosthesis to improve the appearance of teeth. Compend Contin Educ Dent 2000;21:1008-10:1012.
9. Blair FM, Thomason JM, Smith DG. The flange prosthesis. Dent Update 1996;23:196-199.
10. Mekayarajjananonth T, Kiat-amnuay S, Sooksuntisakoonchai N, Salinas TJ. The functional and esthetic deficit replaced with an acrylic resin gingival veneer. Quintessence Int 2002;33:91-94.

11. Greene PR. The flexible gingival mask: An aesthetic solution in periodontal practice. Br Dent J 1998;184: 536-540.
12. Priest GF, Lindke L. Gingival-colored porcelain for implant-supported prostheses in the aesthetic zone. Pract Periodontics Aesthet Dent 1998;10:1231-1240.
13. Hannon SM, Colvin CJ, Zurek DJ. Selective use of gingival-toned ceramics: Case reports. Quintessence Int 1994;25:s233-238.
14. Cairo F, Rotundo R, Miller PD, Pini Prato GP. Root coverage esthetic score: A system to evaluate the esthetic outcome of the treatment of gingival recession through evaluation of clinical cases. J Periodontol 2009; 80:705-710.
15. Ellis SG, Sharma P, Harris IR. Case report: Aesthetic management of a localised periodontal defect with a gingival veneer prosthesis. Eur J Prosthodont Restor Dent 2000;8: 23-26.
16. Nair C, Dange SP. Aesthetic management of gingival recession: A flexible gingival mask. J Indian Prosthodont Soc 2003;3:34-35.